

CAREER ASPIRATIONS IN RELATION TO PARENTAL SUPPORT AMONG ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study is designed to understand the Career aspirations of adolescent students in relation to parental support. The population of the study consisted of all the students of class 9th of government senior secondary schools of Gurdaspur district, Punjab. In order to conduct the survey, a sample of 200 students (Both male and female) was collected from three government senior secondary schools. The present study revealed that there exists significant difference in parental support of secondary school students with respect to type of schools, but there exists no significant difference with respect to locale. Further, no significant difference was found in career aspiration of secondary school students with respect to locale and type of schools. This study also revealed that there exists no significant relationship between career aspiration and parental support of secondary school students.

Key words: - Career aspiration, parental support, Adolescent students.

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Introduction: -

A career can be defined as the sequence and variety of occupations undertaken for a significant period of a person's life and with opportunities for progress. More broadly, 'career' includes life roles, leisure activities, learning and work. It includes the sum total of paid and unpaid work, learning and life roles you undertake throughout your life. The term 'career' was traditionally associated with paid employment and referred to a single occupation. In today's world of work the term 'career' is seen as a continuous process of learning and development. As you gain more experience in the world of work and undertake a variety of life experiences, you are building your unique career path. All life experiences, including paid work, sporting interests and managing a household should be drawn upon as evidence to a potential employer that you are the person for the job. Career aspirations are vision for future. They are what you hope to achieve in your professional life in the years to come. Career aspirations are an individual's expressed choices or goals in the vocational domain (Rojewski, 2005). Setting career goals is important to the development of vocational identity (Erikson, 1968), and is a crucial part of career preparation, as these goals are the forerunners to adult career choices and life successes (Schoon & Parsons, 2002). A career aspiration is a long-term dream that you are pursuing. A goal is usually a more specific, short-term objective with a detailed plan for achieving it. According to (Brien, 2001) career aspiration is a desire to pursue higher education after high schools, such as a four-year college; two-year College or a vocational school in order

to increase career possibilities. During adolescence, developing a vocational identity is a central developmental task. As a child's first experience of relationship generally occurs within the family, parental support is necessary in helping the child to achieving his career aspirations. Parental support has been defined as "parental support toward the child, such as praising, encouraging and physical affection, which indicate to the child that he or she is accepted and loved" (Barnes, 2000: 176). Although support from peers' gains in importance during adolescence, parental support continues to be beneficial. Family is an enduring association of parent and off springs whose primary function is the socialization of the child and satisfaction of the members. However, to understand the influence of the family on the child, it is important to understand family and its functions. In the family, the role of mother in the development of the child is very vital. A child usually spends maximum time with his mother. Not only mother, father also leaves a strong and long-lasting impact on the child and lays the foundation for his future development. A child's first line of protection and care should be the family. For the full and harmonious development of the personality of a child, it should grow up in a family environment, in an atmosphere of happiness, love and understanding. Family is a small intimate group of basic setting within which most children come in contact with society where they learn how to behave within a society and outside world. Support from parents gains in importance during adolescence, because during this stage, students go through various physical, mental, emotional and social changes. A Career preparation in adolescence is an important precursor for successful career development across the lifespan and is closely related to adolescent.

The stage of adolescence is a very important period of human development. It is often referred to as the spring of human life. The word adolescence comes from a Greek word "adolescere" which means "to grow to maturity". It is a transitional phase of physical and mental human development generally occurring between puberty and legal adulthood. The name of G. Stanley Hall (1904) is of great significance in studies related to adolescence as he was the first psychologist who devoted much of his time in collecting data on adolescence. He wrote two volumes in 1904 on psychology of adolescence which contributed significantly to the study of adolescents. His pioneering work on adolescence was ground breaking laying the foundation for subsequent studies on child behaviour. His views on adolescence as "a period of storm and stress" aptly sums up this stage in an individual's life as the individual enters a new and powerful phase in his life causing upheavals and turmoil's in all aspects of development be it physical, mental, social and emotional. According to A.T. Jersild (1978), "Adolescence is that span of years during which boys and girls move from childhood to adulthood, mentally, emotionally, socially and physically." Dorothy Rogers defines adolescence as, "a process rather than a period, a process of achieving the attitudes and beliefs needed for effective participation in the society. The World Health Organisation (W.H.O.) identifies adolescence as the period in human growth and development that occurs after childhood and before adulthood from ages 10-19.

The parent-adolescent relationship content has been noted as a primary influence on career goals (Kerpelman and Schvaneveldth, 1999; Otto, 2000; Paa and Mcwhirter, 2000, Hargrove, Creagh and Burgers, 2002; Creamer and Laughlin, 2005). It has been found that parents tend to create the strongest influence on their adolescent's vocational choice more than any other group including counselors, teachers, friends, or even people working in the identified occupations of desire (Bardick, Bernes, Magnusson & Wilko, 2004). Young et al (2001) illustrated the influence of parents on adolescents career aspirations in their novel study of career development as a family project. Small and Mcclean (2002) reported on the very strong influence parents can have by providing an example. The influence of school teaches on career

choice is far less than that of parents. Findings of Kniveton (2004) supports Wintre etal (1988), who reported, that in things like career choice parents still had a role to play. The study throws light on the influence of environmental factor of which parents are an important component in an adolescent's career decision making process.

It has been observed that most adolescents are very much dependent on their parents in making their career choice. All parents more or less have aspirations for their children's educational and occupational attainment. How their aspirations influence an adolescent's career choice is of immense significance. Parent's role in this is very vital decision in their offspring's lives will have a long-term implication on an adolescent's future life. Hence, studying the influence of parental support on an adolescent's career choice is of immense significance. Hence, the need was felt to make a humble attempt to take up this area for research.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study career aspirations among secondary school students with respect to locale and type of school.
2. To study parental support among secondary school students with respect to locale and type of school.
3. To find out the relationship of career aspiration and parental support of secondary school students.

HYPOTHESES

1. There exists no significant difference in career aspirations among secondary school students with respect to locale and type of school.
2. There exists no significant difference in parental support among secondary school students with respect to locale and type of school.
3. There exists no significant relationship between career aspiration and parental support of secondary school students.

METHDOLOGY

Study design: Descriptive method of research was used for the study.

SAMPLE AND SELECTION CRITERIA

The sample of the study included three government senior secondary school students selected through non random sampling technique.

STATISTICAL TOOLS

Following statistical tools have been used:

1. t-test was used to study significant difference between adolescents boys and girls.
2. One-Way ANOVA was used to study significant difference between types of schools i.e., Boys school, Girls school, Co-education school.
3. Correlation was used to see relationship between career aspiration and parental support.

RESEARCH TOOLS

TOOL 1 Career Aspiration Scale by Anand (2014).

TOOL 2 Parental Support Scale by Nandwana & Asawa (2012).

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA*Table 1: SIGNIFICANCE OF DIFFERENCE IN CAREER ASPIRATIONS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO LOCALE AND TYPE OF SCHOOL*

	Group	N	Mean	SD	P-value	SE	F-ratio
Overall CA of locale	Urban	140	94.5		7.50		0.633
	Rural	60	96.7	7.53	0.058		0.972
School							
Overall CA of Type of school	Girls1	70	95.2		8.06		0.964
	Boys2	70	95.9	7.61	0.43		0.909
	Co-Ed3	60	94.2		6.88		0.888

The table 1 reveals that calculated p-value 0.058 was found to be more than at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, it reveals that there is no significant difference in career aspirations among secondary school students with respect to locale. Further, the table 1 reveals that calculated p-value 0.433 was found to be more than at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, it reveals that there is no significant difference in career aspiration among secondary school students with respect to type of school.

Hence H_1 , there exists no significant difference in career aspirations among secondary school students with respect to locale and type of school is not rejected.

SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE IN PARENTAL SUPPORT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO LOCALE AND TYPE OF SCHOOL.

	Group	N	Mean value	p-	SD	SE	F-ratio
Overall PS locale	Urban	140	77.4			0.566	
	Rural	60	76.7	0.472	4.92	0.635	
School							
Overall PS	Girls 1	70	77.5		6.70	0.800	
	Boys 2	70	75.7	0.024	5.78	0.691	3.82
	Co Edu 3	60	78.5		5.84	0.753	

The table 2 reveals that calculated p-value 0.472 was found to be more then at 0.05 level of significance. The table 2 further reveals that calculated p-value 0.024 was found to be less then at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, it reveals that there is significant difference in

parental support among secondary school students with respect to type of school. The study further reveals that students of co-education school received higher parental support as compared to students of boys and girls schools. Hence H_2 , there exists no significant difference in parental support among secondary school students with respect to type of school is rejected, but the hypothesis there exists no significant difference in parental support among secondary school students with respect to locale is not rejected.

TABLE 3: SIGNIFICANCE OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CAREER ASPIRATION AND PARENTAL SUPPORT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.

Correlation Matrix		
OVERALL PS		
OVERALL PS	Pearson's r	-
	Df	-
	p-value	-
OVERALL CA	Pearson's r	0.077
	Df	198
	p-value	0.281

Table 3 reveals that calculated p-value 0.281 was found to be more than at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, it reveals that there is no significant relationship between career aspiration and parental support of secondary school students.

Hence H_3 , there exists no significant relationship between career aspiration and parental support of secondary school students is not rejected.

FINDINGS

- The present study revealed that career aspirations of secondary school students do not differ with respect to locale and type of schools.
- The present study revealed that parental support of secondary school students do not differ with respect to locale, but differ with respect to type of schools.
- The present study revealed that there exists no correlation between career aspiration and parental support

CONCLUSION

Career aspiration is an important decision in an adolescent's life and choosing the appropriate career will have far reaching effect in an adolescent's future life. Parents should be made to understand that career development issues are important during early adolescent stage and not just when their children reach the high school stage. Creating a congenial parent-adolescent relationship by displaying behaviours which are beneficial for maintaining that relationship is very much necessary for parents. Children should be initiated into a career education programme right from the primary stage so that they may be introduced into various aspects of career aspirations such as awareness of different career roles and discover their aptitudes and capabilities and thereby make the right choice when they reach that stage.

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